

Original Research

Tertiary Education and Economic Growth in Tanzania

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Abstract

The study examines how tertiary education impact economic growth in Tanzania, time series secondary data spanning from the year 1999 to 2023 were extracted from World Bank database. Key explanatory variables were tertiary enrollment and government spending on tertiary education while dependent variable was economic performance measured by growth of gross domestic product. There were control variables such as inflation rate and population growth rate. After normalization of data, unit root test was performed and all variables were stationary after first difference. The study engaged bounds test for Autoregressive Distributed Lags (ARDL) Model and Error correction model as the results of existence of the co-integrating equations among the variables in the long run. Findings reveal that increase in expenditure on education and higher enrollment in tertiary education significantly enhance economic progress overtime. Conversely, short-term effects of educational investments are not immediately evident. Policy implications suggest that sustained investment in education, enhancing access and quality of tertiary education, and fostering public-private partnerships in education sector are crucial for long-term economic development. These insights underscore the pivotal role of education in driving economic prosperity.

Keywords: Economic Performance, Expenditure on Tertiary Education, Enrolment, Tanzania.

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Introduction

Expenditure on education is important for the development of many countries in the world. Investment in human capital through education is fundamental for social and economic development since economic growth is translated by human capital, thus, investment in education becomes crucial (Angrist et al., 2021; Card, 2018). In 2022 the expenditure on education in developed countries such as United States contributed 5.5% of total GDP while for European Countries and Central Asia was 4.5% (World Bank, 2024). General trend indicates globally, spending on education has been increasing over time, though there was slight regress during the year 2019 and 2020 as the result of COVID-19 pandemic and continued to increase from 2021 onward (Global Education Monitoring Report, 2023). Government spending on education in countries under the Organization for Economic Cooperation Development (OECD) has been proportion with increased enrolment rate and the focus is to produce more human capital responsible enhance economic performance through high productivity (Hajebi et al., 2023). This means that, governments are necessitated to continue investing in education for future economic benefits obtained from transformation made by skilled human capital.

The increase in spending on education has also been established globally to be direct proportional with population increase, thus allocation of more budgets has been a cornerstone in achieving educational goals (Global Education Monitoring Report, 2023). For the past decade (2012 – 2021), huge spending on education has been incurred by various countries grouped together based on their income status. For instance, countries with low income spent USD 29 billion while USD 454 was spent by lower middle income, USD 1.58 trillion was spent by upper middle income and USD 3.37 trillion by high income countries (Global Education Monitoring Report, 2023).

In African countries like South Africa, expenditure on education contributes to 6.2% of total GDP in 2022 and for East African countries, the contribution of expenditure on education in 2022 was as follows; Kenya (4.1%), Burundi (4.9%), Rwanda (4.9%), Uganda (2.6%) and South Sudan (1.6%). In Tanzania, expenditure on education in 2022 was 3.2% of total GDP (World Bank, 2024). Despite the fact that Tanzania government has been funding other developmental sectors' projects, still expenditure on education has almost remained fairly constant for the period of five years; in 2018 (3.7%), 2019 (3.6%), 2020 (3.2%), 2021 (3.1%) and 2022 (3.2%), inferring that expenditure on education is crucial for GDP growth. In connection, expenditure on education goes in parallel with students' enrolment. In Tanzania, for the past five years, the students' enrolment trend in higher education institutions (HEIs) expressed significant increase; in 2018/2019 (216,901), 2019/2020 (233,734), 2020/2021 (259,266), 2021/2022 (295,919) and 2021/2023 (314,643) (TCU Report, 2023). Such students' increase in enrolment should reflect increase in expenditure on education, consequently reflecting GDP growth. The detailed illustrations on tertiary expenditure, students' enrolment and economic performance in Tanzania are presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Trend of tertiary expenditure and economic performance
 Sources: (1) Data extracted from World Bank Dataset (2024)
 (2) Extracted from the Tanzania Commission for Universities (2023)

While students’ enrolment in tertiary education in Tanzania has appreciated, in a real fact, it has been in line with the population growth from which students are derived. In this concern, population increase was also connected in the focus of this study as the control variable. The study by Loiboo et al., (2022). augmented this thinking since it cemented that economic growth is the function of population growth, the later, fuel economic development. The World meter (2024) inform that Tanzania population will continue increasing from 69,419,073 in 2024 to 71,427,810 in 2025 and it is forecasted to reach 129,931,520 in 2050. With these population increase statistic, dedication of the Tanzania government to continue investing in education including tertiary education will be inevitable, given the importance of skilled human capital in fueling economic performance across the years of projection. Tanzania historical population growth from 1955 to 2024 is presented in Figure 2 for clarity.

Figure 2. Trend of the Tanzania population
 Source: Extracted from World meter (2024) and computed by authors

The government of Tanzania has put in place several initiatives to ensure alignment between expenditure on education and students’ enrolment and future implication on GDP growth. The highlighted initiatives include increased budget annually, total budget that allocated for education sector in 2022/2023 budget was TZS 5.637 trillion, the budget which was higher by 0.97% as compared to TZS 5.583 of 2021/2022 (Policy

Forum, 2023), continuous efforts in funding expenditure on education (World Bank, 2024), improved trends in students' enrolment (TCU, 2023). Further, various previous studies have been carried out to address issues of expenditure in education and growth of GDP (World Bank, 2024), budget allocation by the government (Policy Forum, 2023), trend of students' enrolment in tertiary education in Tanzania (2023). Despite government's initiatives and existing studies undertaken recently on expenditure in education and economic growth, most of the studies have concentrated on education as a whole without being specific on tertiary education and economic growth. Furthermore, some studies focus on students' enrolment in higher education without focusing on tertiary education in connection with economic growth and some focused-on university education while ignoring non-university higher learning institutions (World Bank, 2024; TCU, 2023; Policy Forum, 2023). For example, Bwana (2012) examined how expenditure on education and capital formation impact economic growth in Tanzania, using time series data from 1990 to 2020 in VAR -model, the study did not separate spending on tertiary and non- tertiary education. Findings revealed that lagged value of economic performance and capital formation does not have any significant impact on the spending on education in the short run. Bikiombe (2021) also assessed the influence of government spending on education and economic progress in Tanzania, without separating expenditure on what level of education as it is clear that in Tanzania education is categorized into three levels. Findings revealed that there is existence of relationship between spending on education and economic growth over time. In a study by Peter and Seebens,(2003) impact of primary school enrollment on the economic performance was examined and findings revealed that school enrollment contribute to human capital development and therefore over time it has influence on the economic progress . However, the study did not consider enrollment in tertiary education. Therefore, this study mainly focusses on enrollment in tertiary education as one of the independent variables that contribute to economic growth.

In light of this, the study examines the relationship between the tertiary education and economic development. Specifically, the study aimed to (i) examine the impact of expenditure in tertiary education on economic performance and (ii) examine the impact of students' enrolment in tertiary education on economic performance. This study will be of great significance in several angles including demonstration of the critical impact of educational investment on economic performance in Tanzania. The study also will highlight long-term benefits of increased expenditure and higher enrolment in tertiary education, and it will underscore role of education as a key driver of economic prosperity. Further, the study will offer a compelling case for prioritizing educational reforms and investments.

Methodology

The study period covers the year 1999 to 2023, data were extracted from world development indicators data base. Variables of interest were growth of gross domestic product as proxy of economic performance. While government spending on tertiary education and tertiary enrollment were used as the key independent variables. Population growth rate and inflation rate were used as the control variables.

$$\text{LnGDP} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{LnEXPT} + \beta_2 \text{LnENRT} + \beta_3 \text{LnPLNG} + \beta_4 \text{LnINFL} + \mu \dots (1)$$

Were

LnGDPG- represents natural log of growth of gross domestic product (in USD)

LnEXPT -represents natural log of expenditure on tertiary education (in USD)

LnENRT- represents natural log of enrollment in tertiary education

LnPLNG - represents natural log of population growth rate

LnINFL -represents inflation rate (as measured as consumer price index)

In equation (1) Gross domestic product growth (GDPG) is expressed as a function of expenditure on tertiary education; enrollment on tertiary education; population growth and inflation rate.

It is very essential to note that the gross domestic product growth rate (GDPG) is just one of many indicators used to assess economic performance. Other variables may include gross domestic product per capital as well as human development index. Gross domestic product is widely used measure of economic indicator by United Nations System of National Accounts. It represents the total output of goods and services of a state during a certain period of time. It is used for benchmarking the economic performance of states, and sometimes it is broadened to evaluate and make estimates of living standards, progress or social welfare between states, although GDP was not originally developed for this purpose. Questioning the use of GDP for this purpose and its relevance has gained ground slowly. For example, increased awareness of global warming and the most recent financial crisis have been a major thrust to research more different methods of measuring welfare, rather than production. This study opted to use GDPG as a measure of economic performing due to availability of data (Tjukanov, 2011). Researchers have continued to broaden the link between economic performance and various factors such as institutional quality. For example, Chong & Calderón (2000) carried out a cross sectional study linking the growth and institutional quality (such as measure of corruption, bureaucratic quality, property rights) with economic performance. Their findings revealed that economic growth does have influence on the institutional quality.

Normality

Before performing the analysis, data are supposed to be declared as time series data. Analysis of data is usually preceded with some basic tests (such as normality and stationarity test). Though many attributes (such as heights, weights, marks scores) follow normal distribution it is still recommended to confirm before carrying out data analysis (Weisstein, 2021). If data are not normally distributed, we apply natural logarithm to the variables in order to normalize them. According to Hatem et al., (2022) there are several ways through which normality test can be measured, some methods involve numerical and some are involving visualizations. This study adopted Skewness-Kurtosis test to perform normality test whereby we test null hypothesis that variables are not normally distributed against the alternative hypothesis that the variables are normally distributed. (*Ho: variables are not normally distributed, against the*

alternative H1: variables are normally distributed). We normally reject the null hypothesis if the joint probability is significant. Which implies that the variable is normally distributed if the null hypothesis is rejected. Variable is considered to be normally distributed if the null hypothesis is rejected.

Multicollinearity test

Prior to examining the stationarity of our variables, it is important to note that our data follows a time series structure and determine if the independent variables exhibit multicollinearity using correlation analysis. Given the fact that this study incorporates multivariate time series data with five variables, we conducted tests to assess the presence of multicollinearity. Multicollinearity can lead to problem when fitting the model or interpreting the results. To assess the extent of multicollinearity among the explanatory variables, we performed a correlation analysis. If the correlations among the variables is less than 80 percent it implies that there is no serious correlation among independent variables, we further confirm the result using VIF test. According to Daoud, (2017) if two or more than two explanatory variables are highly correlated, it implies that the relationships between dependent variables and independent variables will be distorted by the strong relationships among the independent variables. Srisa-An, (2021) also added that in modelling time series data, multicollinearity is an obstacle to accuracy.

Unit root test

Time series data in most cases experience the problem of stationarity and therefore the use of non-stationary variables in time series may bring wrong results which may mislead in case of precise decision making (Asghar et al., 2012). Existing literature suggests various methods that exist for testing the stationarity of variables, with the Augmented Dickey-Fuller and Philip Perron tests being the most widely employed techniques (Dickey & Fuller, 1979). Hence, this research employed the Augmented Dickey-Fuller test to assess the stationarity of the variables.

The rule is that, if the absolute value of the test statistics falls below the 5 percent critical value, it indicates a lack of stationarity, and vice versa. If the result of the test revealed that variables are stationary at level, it implies variables are integrated of order zero I (0) while if the result indicate that none of the variables exhibited stationarity at the initial level it is necessary to apply differencing to attain stationarity. If all variables are stationary after first difference, it implies that they are integrated of order one I (1) and then it is important to perform Johansen co-integration test to test existence of the cointegrating equations. If the variables are cointegrated at mixed level (mixed order) bounds test for cointegration is performed to test existence of long run relationship (Pesaran et al., 2001). If the bounds test for cointegration exhibit long run relationships we perform Autoregressive lags (ARDL model) by restricting 2 lags

Results and Discussions

This paper aimed at estimating the role of tertiary education on economic development. Before performing the key analysis, we perform a number of tests in order

to understand the characteristics of the data and eventually determine the appropriate model selection.

Normality tests

Our variables were tested for normality using the skewness and kurtosis tests. The results showed that all the variables at their row form were not normally distributed. This was followed by normalizing them by converting them into the log form as a corrective measure. The log forms of the variables were now tested once again and they were all found to be normally distributed. Applying logarithm forms is widely used for the measurements which require correction before detailed analysis or evaluation (Bornemann & Doveton, 1981).

Unit root tests

Unit root in times series data signifies that the data are not stationary. A test of unit root determines the appropriate model for analyzing the times series data. The Augmented Dickey-Fuller test was used and the results were as presented as seen in Table 1

Table 1. Unit test Results

Variables	AT Level		After First Difference	
	Test statistic	5% Critical value	Test Statistic	5% Critical Value
(1) <i>lnGDPgrw</i>	3.107*	3.000	N/A	N/A
(2) <i>lnEXPTed</i>	2.245	3.000	5.340*	3.000
(3) <i>lnENRT</i>	1.406	3.000	9.229*	3.000
(4) <i>lnPLNG</i>	1.471	3.000	3.509*	3.000
(5) <i>lnINFL</i>	1.879	3.000	5.315*	3.000

*denotes that test statistic is greater than the 5% critical value and therefore variable is stationary.

From the results presented in Table 1 only one variable (*LnGDPgrw*) the log of GDP growth) was stationary at level (Integrated of order zero I (0)). All the remaining variables were stationary after the first difference or in other words they were integrated of order one (I (1)). This gave us a lee way to proceed with the Autoregressive distributed lag model (ARDL) since it is recommended for estimations with a mixed order of integration.

Multicollinearity Test

To estimate the correlation between each pair of the variables, the matrix of correlation was used generated. The results as seen in table 2 show that no pair of the variables had a correlation exceeding the critical level 80%. This implies that there is no critical multicollinearity. These results were again confirmed using the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) test. The test again revealed no serious multicollinearity as there was no VIF greater than 10.

Table 2. Matrix of correlation

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
(1) lnGDPgrw	1.000				
(2) lnEXPTed	0.587	1.000			
(3) lnENRT	-0.378	-0.469	1.000		
(4) lnPLNG	-0.071	-0.122	0.702	1.000	
(5) lnINFL	0.259	0.249	-0.207	-0.352	1.000

The Bounds test for Cointegration

It was also important to assure ourselves about the existence of short run or both short run and long run relationships between our variables (Pesaran et al., 2001). This also is consistent with the approach employed in the study by (Philips, 2018). Odhiambo (2022) further stressed that the ARDL-bounds test is much appropriate if the sample size is relatively small. ARDL Bounds Test revealed that the F statistic was greater than the lower bound and the t statistic was less than the lower bound. This made us conclude that there was a long run relationship. This being the case, we estimated the ARDL model with the Error correction component in order to capture the long run relationship in the variables.

ARDL Regression Model Results

The ARDL (1,2,2,2,2) regression was estimated to obtain the relationship between the dependent variable and the independent variables of the study. The results were presented as seen in table 4.3. The results showed that the Error Correction term (ECT) was significant and had a negative coefficient signifying that our model was correctly specified. It also shows that the speed of adjustment towards the long run equilibrium is 107%.

Long run relationship

The long run relationship shows that three independent variables had a significant influence on the explained variable.

The log of expenditure in education (*lnEXPTed*) was found to be positively and significantly influencing economic performance (*lnGDPgrw*). This implies that overtime, the elasticity of economic performance with respect to changes in expenditure on education is 1.6. Intuitively this implies an elastic relationship meaning that, a proportionately small change in expenditure in education leads to a proportionately large change in economic growth in the long run. This finding conforms with the findings of the study by Liana et al., (2013) which revealed existence of strong positive influence of expenditure on education and economic progress in European countries. Finding is also consistent with what Bloom et al., (2014) revealed in their study which tried to investigate the role of higher education in economic progress. They added that spending in higher education support the technological catch-up which eventually minimize the knowledge gap and increase rapid economic development.

The Log of enrollment in tertiary education (*lnENRT*) was also found to be positively and significantly impacting changes on economic performance. In other words, in the long run, the elasticity of the economic performance with respect to changes in the enrollment in tertiary education is 0.94. This is a relatively inelastic relationship but since the number approaches 1, we can likely interpret it as a unitary elastic relationship. It likely implies that, as a change in enrollment in the tertiary education leads to a proportionately same change in the economic performance in the long run. This finding is more the same as the findings by Mthembu, (2015) where the influence of spending on education and enrollment in higher education on innovation and economic growth was examined in South Africa using the data time series data from 1983-2012. VECM and ARDL suggested a strong long run cointegrating relationship between economic growth, labor capital, enrollment in education, expenditure on education and innovation in South Africa.

Short Run Relationship

In the short run both first and the second lags of the of the government expenditure on education (*lnEXPTed – D & LD*) could not influence significant changes on the economic performance. This is likely because the investment in education is not likely to impact changes in the economy in the short run. For the impact to be seen, the education obtained should yield positive changes which will thereafter be witnessed in the long run.

Table 3. ARDL (1,2,2,2,2) Regression results

		Coefficient	Standard Error	t	P>t
ADJ					
	lnGDPgrw				
	L1.	-1.072**	0.352	-3.050	0.023
LR					
	lnEXPTed	1.559**	1.221	-0.460	0.043
	lnENRT	0.947**	0.385	2.460	0.049
	lnPLNG	-2.605	1.706	-1.530	0.178
	lnINFL	-0.894	0.295	-3.030	0.023
SR					
	lnEXPTed				
	D1.	0.894	0.893	1.000	0.356
	LD.	0.687	0.478	1.440	0.201
	lnENRT				
	D1.	1.329**	0.396	-3.360	0.015
	LD.	-0.402	0.253	-1.590	0.163
	lnPLNG				
	D1.	-1.005	1.877	-0.540	0.612
	LD.	1.616	1.508	1.070	0.325

		Coefficient	Standard Error	t	P>t
	lnINFL				
	D1.	0.715*	0.348	2.060	0.085
	LD.	0.272	0.184	1.480	0.189
	Constant	29.345	17.764	1.650	0.150

*, **, & *** denotes significance level at 1% 5% and 10% respectively. On the other hand, the first lag of the log of enrollment in tertiary education (lnENRT – D1) had a positive significant relationship with economic performance. This is to mean that the elasticity of economic performance with respect to changes in enrollment in tertiary education is 1.3. This is an elastic relationship. It likely implies that, a proportionately small change in the enrollment in tertiary education, brings about a proportionately larger change in economic performance in the short run. This finding is consistent with Abdelgany et al., (2024) where the relationship between the education spending and economic growth using ARDL-bounds test was examined in Egypt. It was revealed that in the short run there is positive influence of enrollment in education and economic growth.

Post Estimation Diagnostic Tests

To be assured of our model results, a number of diagnostic tests were conducted, the normality of the residuals was tested using the skewness and kurtosis tests for normality. The results showed that the residuals were white noise and therefore our results can be trusted. We further conducted two robustness tests through dropping the control variables one after another in each model. The results of the new models (Not presented here) showed that the parameter estimates changed in small percentages but their level of significance remained the same. The overall model significance also remained unaffected.

Conclusion and Recommendation

The analysis of both long-run and short-run relationships between educational investment and economic performance reveals distinct impacts over different time horizons. In the long run, all the key independent variables exhibit significant influence on economic growth. Notably, the log of expenditure in education demonstrates a positive and significant effect on economic performance, with an elasticity of 1.6. This suggests an elastic relationship where a relatively small increase in education expenditure results in a disproportionately larger enhancement in economic growth. Additionally, the log of enrollment in tertiary education also significantly and positively affects economic performance, with an elasticity of 0.94. Although this indicates a nearly unitary elastic relationship, it implies that changes in tertiary enrollment are closely mirrored by changes in economic performance. Therefore, education is a multifaceted driver of economic growth, influencing it through various channels such as human capital development, innovation, social stability, institutional quality, and social capital. Theoretical frameworks provide different lenses through which to understand

the mechanisms by which education impacts economic growth, but they collectively underscore the centrality of education in fostering long-term economic development.

Conversely, in the short run, neither the immediate nor the lagged effects of government expenditure on education significantly influence economic performance. This finding highlights the temporal lag in educational investments translating into economic benefits, suggesting that the positive impacts of education on the economy are predominantly realized in the long run. Overall, these insights underscore the importance of sustained investment in education to foster long-term economic growth.

Policy Implications

Based on the analysis of the long-run and short-run relationships between spending on educational and economic performance, several policy implications can be drawn for the relevant authorities. Given the significant long-run impact of education expenditure on economic performance, relevant authorities should advocate for increased and sustained investment in the tertiary education. This includes budget allocations aimed at improving educational infrastructure, faculty development, and learning resources to ensure quality education. The positive relationship between tertiary education enrollment and economic growth highlights the need to increase access to higher education. Both regulators should work on expanding capacity of existing tertiary education institutions, and establishing new institutions that reflect new skills needed in the market in order to promote production. Government may offer more scholarships and financial aid, and implementing policies that encourage higher enrollment rates. Regulators should also continually update curricula to align with industry demands and enhance vocational and academic programs that equip students with practical and theoretical skills. In order to achieve expected outcome responsible ministry should also establish robust systems for monitoring and evaluating the effectiveness of educational programs and expenditures. By tracking progress and outcomes.

This study recommends collaborations between the government, private sector, and international organizations to leverage additional resources and expertise. Such collaborations will reduce burden to the government while encourage more investments in education. For example, such partnerships can support infrastructure development, provide internships and job placements for students, and foster innovation in education delivery. Since the long-term benefits are clear, there is a need of having supportive policies for short term impact of education expenditure and enrollment on economic growth in the short run. For example, having targeted vocational and higher education programs that address immediate skill gaps in the labor market, thus providing quick economic benefits. The study further recommends the need to continue raising awareness among policymakers, stakeholders, and the public about the significant economic returns from investing in tertiary education. This can help to broaden support for educational reforms and funding. This will help in building a skilled workforce that can drive economic growth across different sectors.

Author Contributions

As far as the data collection is concerned, Dr. Mashenene was largely involved in preparation of checklist that was used during data collection, data collection and data cleaning before the analysis. Dr. Kembo M. Bwana was largely involved in methodology and research design while Mr. Jeremiah concentrated in data analysis and discussion.

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References

- Abdelgany, M., Mohamed, S., & Rashed, M. (2024). Evaluating the Relationship Between Education Spending and Economic Growth in Egypt: An ARDL Model Analysis. *International Journal of Economics, Finance and Management Sciences*, 12(2), 66–92. <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.ijefm.20241202.13>
- Angrist, N., Djankov, S., Goldberg, P. K., & Patrinos, H. A. (2021). Measuring human capital using global learning data. *Nature*, 592(7854), 403–408.
- Asghar, N., Awan, A., & Rehman, H. U. (2012). Health/Growth Dynamics in Pakistan: A Simultaneous Model. *Actual Problems of Economics*, 138, 276–285.
- Bikiombe, K. (2021). *Effect of Education Sector Expenditure on Economic Growth in Tanzania* (Doctoral dissertation).
- Bwana, K. M. (2022, August). Expenditure on Education, Capital Formation and Economic Growth in Tanzania. In *Applied Research Conference in Africa* (pp. 636-649). Cham: Springer International Publishing.
- Bloom, D. E., Canning, D., Chan, K. J., & Luca, D. L. (2014). Higher education and economic growth in Africa. *International Journal of African Higher Education*, 1(1), 22–57.
- Bornemann, E., & Doveton, J. H. (1981). Log normalization by trend surface analysis. *The Log Analyst*, 22(04). <https://onepetro.org/petrophysics/article-abstract/171817/Log-Normalization-By-Trend-Surface-Analysis>
- Card, D. (2018). Returns to Schooling. In the New Palgrave. *Dictionary of Economics*.
- Chong, A., & Calderón, C. (2000). Causality and Feedback Between Institutional Measures and Economic Growth. *Economics & Politics*, 12(1), 69–81. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1468-0343.00069>

- Daoud, J. I. (2017). Multicollinearity and regression analysis. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 949(1), 012009.
<https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1742-6596/949/1/012009/meta>
- Dickey, D. A., & Fuller, W. A. (1979). Distribution of the Estimators for Autoregressive Time Series with a Unit Root. *Journal of the American Statistical Association*, 74(366a), 427–431.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/01621459.1979.10482531>
- Hajebi, E., Billing, C., & Hajebi, M. (2023). The Effect of Government Expenditure on Education on the Enrollment Rate of Different Educational Levels in Selected OECD Countries. *International Journal of Scientific Research and Management (IJSRM)*, 11(05), 2783–2795.
- Hatem, G., Zeidan, J., Goossens, M., & Moreira, C. (2022). Normality testing methods and the importance of skewness and kurtosis in statistical analysis. *BAU Journal-Science and Technology*, 3(2), 7.
- Liana, S. O. N., NOJA, G. G., Ritivoiu, M., & Tolteanu, R. (2013). Education and economic growth: An empirical analysis of interdependencies and impacts based on panel data. *Timisoara Journal of Economics and Business*, 6(19), 39–54.
- Loiboo, D., Luvanda, E., & Osoro, N. (2022). Population and economic growth in Tanzania. *Tanzania Journal for Population Studies and Development*, 28(2).
<http://www.journals.udsm.ac.tz/index.php/tjpsd/article/view/4850>
- Mthembu, M. S. (2015). *The impact of Education Expenditure, Tertiary Enrolment and Innovation on Economic Growth in South Africa*. [PhD Thesis].
<https://uzspace.unizulu.ac.za/handle/10530/1374>
- Odhambo, N. M. (2022). Foreign Direct Investment and Economic Growth in Kenya: An Empirical Investigation. *International Journal of Public Administration*, 45(8), 620–631. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01900692.2021.1872622>
- Peter, W and Seebens, H (2003). The impact of increased school enrollment on economic growth in Tanzania. *African Development Review*, 17(2), 274- 301.
- Pesaran, M. H., Shin, Y., & Smith, R. J. (2001). Bounds testing approaches to the analysis of level relationships. *Journal of Applied Econometrics*, 16(3), 289–326.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/jae.616>
- Philips, A. Q. (2018). Have Your Cake and Eat It Too? Cointegration and Dynamic Inference from Autoregressive Distributed Lag Models. *American Journal of Political Science*, 62(1), 230–244. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ajps.12318>
- Srisa-An, C. (2021). Guideline of collinearity-avoidable regression models on time-series analysis. *2021 2nd International Conference on Big Data Analytics and Practices (IBDAP)*, 28–32.
<https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/9552165/>

Tjukanov, T. (2011). *Gross Domestic Product as a modern-day economic indicator*.
<https://www.theseus.fi/bitstream/handle/10024/38524/Topi%20Tjukanov%20-%20Gross%20Domestic%20Product%20as%20a%20Modern-Day%20Economic%20Indicator.pdf?sequence=1>

Weisstein, E. W. (2021). Normal Distribution. *From MathWorld--A Wolfram Web Resource*. <https://mathworld.wolfram.com/NormalDistribution.html>

World Bank (2012). Dataset. Retrieved from
<https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/SE.XPD.TOTL.GD.ZS?locations=TZ>

Worldometer. (2024). *Population of Tanzania (2024 and Historical)*.
[<https://www.worldometers.info/world-population/tanzania-population>]. Site visited on 13/6/2024

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<p>HOW TO CITE THIS ARTICLE</p> <p>Bwana, K., Tumaini, J., & Mashenene, G. (2024). Tertiary Education and Economic Growth in Tanzania. <i>International Journal of Management, Accounting and Economics</i>, 11(11), 1591-1604.</p> <p>DOI: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14032897</p> <p>URL: https://www.ijmae.com/article_208649.html</p>	A square QR code is located in the bottom right corner of the table, which likely links to the article's online version.